

Near-, medium- and long-term impacts of climate change on the thermal energy consumption of buildings in Finland under RCP climate scenarios

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Abstract

The building sector is critical in climate change mitigation by reducing its energy consumption. At the same time, warming climate requires adaptation measures from buildings, making it necessary to study the future thermal energy demand of buildings. This paper studies the impact of climate change on the thermal energy demand of buildings in a heating dominated climate of Finland, under “representative concentration pathway” (RCP) climate scenarios in near- (2030), medium- (2050) and long-term (2080) horizon. Additionally, the impact of the thermal performance level of the buildings is investigated. The thermal energy demand calculation is based on overarching standards from the European “energy performance of buildings” directive. The weather scenarios present both typical and extreme weather years, applied through morphing and future weather data from the Finnish Meteorological Institute. The results show that thermal energy demand in Finland in 2080 can decrease up to 74.6 kWh/m². In addition, the decrease in heating demand will be higher than the increase in cooling demand. Cooling can become the dominant peak in long-term evaluations, especially in the South (Vantaa) with passive buildings under RCP8.5 climate scenario. Renovation is the most efficient action to decrease energy intensity, the earliest it is done the better.

Keywords: Climate change, Climate adaptation, Building energy need, Thermal energy need, Morphing, RCP climate scenario

1. Introduction

Anthropogenic greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions are driving global warming, having increased the global surface temperature by 0.99 °C from 1850–1900 to 2001–2020 [1]. The rise of global surface temperature has caused observable impacts on nature and human systems [2], and the impact of warming is 2-3 times higher in the Arctic region [3]. Even with existing national GHG reduction efforts, the temperature rise will likely reach 1.5 °C during this century [4]. Therefore, mitigation and adaptation actions are needed.

The building sector is responsible for 40 % of the energy consumed and 36 % of energy-related GHG emissions in the European Union (EU) [5]. Therefore, reducing building energy consumption can contribute to climate change mitigation. At the same time, buildings need to adapt to climate change that results in higher moisture contents in the building structures [6] and increased overheating risks [7]. To mitigate climate change, many countries have set building regulations to reduce their energy consumption, notably concerning thermal needs. For instance, the EU has set a GHG reduction target of 55 % by 2030 [8] and climate neutrality by 2050 [9]. To meet these targets, various renovation scenarios have been investigated, especially in heating-dominated countries. These include assessments of emission and power demands in the whole building stock at the national level [10], district heating demand at the city level [11], and cost-efficient renovation of multi-family houses [12] and detached houses [13]. Renovation is vital to reach GHG reduction targets, but scenarios often neglect climate change's impact on weather data and the variance of climate change scenarios. Even when heating demand changes are considered, it does not account for the spatial differences at the national level. In cold climates, building regulations aiming at reducing energy consumption can even increase the overheating risk in buildings [14]. Without including adaptive measures to buildings, discomfort rates will increase, reducing the well-being of inhabitants [15]. It is necessary to include cooling demand when assessing climate change's impact on building energy need, to evaluate not only climate change mitigation but also adaptation. Additionally, the assessment should cover regions of various climates in the same country.

The objectives of this paper are to determine how much the heating and cooling demands in Finland will change under current Representative Concentration Pathway scenarios in near-, medium and long-term horizons, and to assess the impact of energy efficiency improvements on the total and peak thermal demands in future climates. The novelty of this work is the focus on a Nordic country with the inclusion of the different climate regions and newer climate change scenarios (Representative Concentration Pathway) to determine the thermal energy demand changes on a long-term (2080) pathway. The current studies on the future thermal demand of buildings on Nordic countries generally focus on their southern parts, like Växjö [16, 17] and Karlshamn [18] in Sweden, or Vantaa [19] and Helsinki [20, 21] in Finland. Due to the length of these Nordic countries, their climate conditions are not similar between their northern and southern parts, requiring additional research for a more comprehensive analysis on the thermal energy demand development on national-level. More specifically, studies on the topic in Finland, are also either conducted under the old climate change scenarios (Special Report on Emissions Scenarios) [19], or carry only up till 2050 period [20, 21].

For this study, a thermal model was created which can operate with hourly time steps. It is capable of determining the heat demand to keep a constant temperature in the building and of calculating the indoor air and structure material temperatures. Combining this with a smart house model from [22] allows us to utilize realistic, but generated appliance load profiles as internal heat gain sources, as well as utilize them to determine the occupancy of the inhabitants.

2. Methodology

2.1. Thermal model

The thermal energy model for estimating the energy performance of buildings under different hourly weather data and with limited information on the building's structural composition was created based on a set of EU's Energy Performance of Buildings (EPB) standards and local regulation input values as references. Two standards were used: ISO 52016-1 for assessing the building's thermal energy needs and loads as well as internal temperatures, and EN 16798-5-1 for the ventilation heating needs and heat recovery system operation. ISO 52016-1 is a grey-box model, using some approximated values as inputs, allowing its usage for energy performance assessment without detailed technical information on the building structure composition. ISO 52016-1 is based on energy-balance calculations with the possibility of depicting it as a thermal RC-network, and it can operate on an hourly or monthly time steps. Its performance has been compared to simulation results from EnergyPlus [23], TRNSYS [24] and ALMABuild [25], and a simplified RC-model based on the standard with IDA ICE [26]. The findings from Zakula et al. [24] show

ISO 52016-1 standard performing well with heating demand estimation in colder climates. Some discrepancies were also reported due to the lack of dynamic calculation, or its simplified approach to building elements. De Luca et al. [27] found that the ISO 52016-1 model results can be improved by including dynamic approaches to both internal and external convective heat transfers, and by adding dynamic heat transfer and total solar energy transmittance values for windows [24, 28]. Additionally, modeling conductive heat transfer through opaque elements with a more dynamic approach improves the results, but requires more detailed technical information about the building structure [28, 29]. Hence, suitable dynamic approaches were added to the ISO 52016-1 standard calculation to improve its accuracy; such as heat transfer phenomena depicted in Figure 1 of which parts are further discussed in the supplementary material.

Overall, the convective heat transfer through building structures in contact with outdoor air is calculated according to ISO 52016-1, and to ground as a combination of ISO 52016-1 and ISO 13370. Convective heat transfer from the outside surface is based on McAdams equation [30, 31], while air-infiltration is calculated with the AIM-2 model [32] through the protocol described by [33] and modified to a suitable air-infiltration loss for ISO 52016-1. Finally, ventilation operation is based on temperature calculations from EN 16798-5-1, and the loss calculations from ISO 52016-1. The National Building Code of Finland [34] is used in determining defrost and supply air temperatures, as well as the monthly ground temperature. Internal heat gains are based on appliance and occupation profiles created with [22]. Appliances are assumed to generate an equal amount of residual heat to their electricity consumption, and occupants generate heat through their metabolic rates related to activities. The heat gain from people is based on [35] calculation method, derived from [36] and ISO 7730. Finally, space heating and cooling power are determined according to ISO 52016-1.

Figure 1: Description of the included heat transfer phenomena and their calculation sources

2.2. Weather and climate data

Weather data depicts the variations on hourly and annual levels, whereas climate data describes longer-term trends. Weather data contains variations between measuring periods, e.g. annual variations but, in general, changes appear in longer time periods due to the overall climate. This leads to multiple choices for using weather data for building energy system simulations, including data sets containing typical or extreme conditions [37]. Of these, files depicting typical weather conditions are generally used to assess the average performance of a building [38], whereas including extreme weather files provide the option of studying its operational range [39]. We assert that the simulation should be conducted with both typical and extreme weather files to assess to what conditions the building needs to be designed for.

There are multiple options for weather files depicting “typical” conditions, like creating Test Reference Year (TRY) or Typical Meteorological Year (TMY) weather files according to historical data from which a selection of “typical” conditions are done for each month with different weighting factors [37]. Of these weather files, the selection is done by their availability and suitability for the simulation, with preference given to the most recent data. For the extreme weather files, direct historical data is used with the selection based on calculated heating degree days (HDD) and cooling degree days (CDD). The degree days calculations use the methodology from [40] with a base heating temperature of 15 °C and a base cooling temperature of 24 °C. Additionally, peak heating and cooling weather files are used by selecting the year with a day having the lowest/highest average temperature to represent “peak” demand. Overall, this leads to a selection of 6 different extreme weather scenarios:

- Winter1 [W1] is the year with the highest heating demand by heating degree days,
- Winter2 [W2] is the year with the lowest heating demand by heating degree days,
- Winter3 [W3] is the year with the day of lowest average daily temperature to test out peak heating demand,
- Summer1 [S1] is the year with the lowest cooling demand by both cooling degree days and the lowest average monthly temperature,
- Summer2 [S2] is the year with the highest cooling demand by cooling degree days,
- Summer3 [S3] is the year with the day with highest average temperature.

These files are used in the building energy simulations to assess building performance and design. The weather variables used in the simulations are outdoor temperature, global irradiance, and wind speed.

2.3. Future weather data

In addition to running building energy system simulations on existing weather files, future weather data is used to investigate the impact of climate change on the building energy performance and its design. Future weather data is based on projections for changes in weather variables according to three different Representative Concentration Pathway (RCP) scenarios: RCP 2.6, RCP 4.5, and RCP 8.5 with near-term (2030), medium-term (2050), and long-term (2080) time horizon. These RCP scenarios are independently created and are based on future estimates of the CO₂ and GHG emission projections resulting in radiative forcing values of +2.6W/m², +4.5W/m² and +8.5W/m² in 2100, respectively. RCP scenarios are then simulated with Global Climate Models (GCMs) to generate various climate and weather variables for climate change’s impact assessment [41]. The RCP scenario impacts are assessed here with simulations either through existing future weather files, which are in line with their existing weather data counterparts, or creating them through a statistical down-scaling method called morphing [42]. Morphing utilizes existing hourly baseline data and projects the changes in the weather variables on a monthly level. Therefore, it can be used to down-scale climate change projection data, from a monthly to an hourly level, which is more suitable for building energy performance simulations. Morphing is divided into three operations: “shifting”, “stretching”, and “shifting and stretching”. Of these, the third step is used to morph future external temperatures as it allows taking into account changes in both average temperature, calculated according to [42], and the daily temperature variation, calculated according to [43, 44]. Global horizontal irradiation and wind speed utilize the stretching method done according to [42]. As such, the impact of the change can be applied only to the variable values higher than 0 (e.g. there is no solar radiation during nighttime).

Figure 2: Distribution of Finland to representative weather areas (I-IV) and the location to which they are normalized (Decree 1010/2017, Annex 1.)

The projected climate changes in weather are received by calculating the absolute monthly mean values and monthly standard deviations for daily average temperatures for each climate change scenario and each time period from the suitable data set, or directly from the climate change simulation results.

3. Case study: Finland

Finland was selected as a case-study as it is a heating-dominated country, where space heating accounted for 67 % of residential energy consumption in 2021 [45]. Finland is also experiencing larger temperature increases than the global average, especially in the North [46], while future building energy performance assessments have been done mainly for Southern cities [19, 20, 21]. Finland is divided into four climate zones presented in Figure 2, from which zones I and IV were selected for this study because of their differences. The city of Vantaa is studied in Zone I and Sodankylä in Zone IV. The energy efficiency requirements for buildings are the same regardless of the location, but their zonal peak heating power design values will vary. Simulations will be conducted on near-, medium- and long-term horizons, with different climate change scenarios, to optimally determine future building types, and their impacts on energy systems.

3.1. Building types and regulations

The selected building type for this study is a detached house, which is common in Finland. They are studied in three sizes and characteristics, to provide sensitivity analysis on the simulation results. The building sizes and their common characteristics are presented in Table 1. To achieve a better understanding of which type of building is the most energy efficient in current and future weather, three thermal performance levels are considered in the simulations; the first two are selected according to the minimum regulative values from the two legislative periods. The third one satisfies energy efficiency requirements for passive building. The variables impacting the thermal performance of these buildings are presented in Table 2. The changes in the thermal performance are only considered at the basic level through insulation levels, ventilation type, and heat recovery, air-tightness, and glazing. Hence, the impact of energy efficiency improvements obtained through system-specific changes, such as different heating or cooling technologies, is not included in the study.

3.2. Weather Files

As described in subsection 2.2, seven scenarios of typical and extreme weather files are used in the simulations. The typical weather files for all zones were selected to be zonal TRY2020 files, created by [48], depicting a typical weather year for each zone for the 1989-2018 time period. The extreme weather files were selected according to the methodology described in subsection 2.2, with the selection of the representative year done for the 2000-2020 time

Table 1: The common values for the selected buildings. Thermal mass, its distribution and solar absorption value for opaque surfaces are standard values from ISO 52016-1.

Variable	Building 1	Building 2	Building 3
Length of south/north wall	10 m	10 m	10 m
Length of east/west wall	12 m	8 m	10 m
Height	2.5 m	2.5 m	5.5 m
Number of floors	1	1	2
Angle of the roof	8	8	8
Area of the north window	3.75 m ²	3.75 m ²	8.25 m ²
Area of the east window	4.5 m ²	3 m ²	8.25 m ²
Area of the south window	3.75 m ²	3.75 m ²	8.25 m ²
Area of the west window	4.5 m ²	3 m ²	8.25 m ²
Area of the door	1.75 m ²	1.75 m ²	1.75 m ²
Resulting house volume	351 m ³	223 m ³	585 m ³
Air changes per hour	0.5	0.5	0.5
Thermal mass of the walls, $K_{m;wall}$	30.6 Wh/(m ² × K)	30.6 Wh/(m ² × K)	30.6 Wh/(m ² × K)
Thermal mass of the floor, $K_{m;floor}$	69.4 Wh/(m ² × K)	69.4 Wh/(m ² × K)	69.4 Wh/(m ² × K)
Thermal mass of the roof, $K_{m;roof}$	30.6 Wh/(m ² × K)	30.6 Wh/(m ² × K)	30.6 Wh/(m ² × K)
Distribution of the thermal mass in walls	Equally distributed	Equally distributed	Equally distributed
Distribution of the thermal mass in floor	Inside surface	Inside surface	Inside surface
Distribution of the thermal mass in roof	Equally distributed	Equally distributed	Equally distributed
Solar absorption value for opaque surfaces	0.6	0.6	0.6

Table 2: Thermal performance values based on regulations for building types with constructions year Decree 1048/2017, Annex 1 and for Passive from [47]. HRE = Heat Recovery Efficiency, ME = Mechanical Exhaust, A2A = Air-to-air heat transfer. * = Used to calculate the minimum energy efficiency requirement, different from structural minimum value.

Variable	1985	2018	Passive
U-values, $U_{c,eli}$, [W/(m² × K)]			
Wall	0.28	0.17	0.08
Floor	0.36	0.16	0.10
Roof	0.22	0.09	0.07
Windows	2.10	1.00	0.80
Door	1.40	1.00	0.50
Air-leakage			
n_{50} , [1/h]	6.00	-	0.50
q_{50} , [m ³ /(h × m ²)]	-	2.0*	-
Ventilation			
HRE	0	55%	85%
Type	ME	A2A	A2A
Glazing			
g-value	0.63	0.56	0.46

period. Figure 3 shows the annual HDD and CDD values for Vantaa and Sodankylä, which can be used to show the range of results, together with “extreme” monthly and daily values, and Table 3 lists the representative years for

each scenario. HDD and CDD data is based on [49], and other historical data is taken from Finnish Meteorological Institute’s open data repository [50].

Figure 3: Annual HDD and CDD sum for Vantaa and Sodankylä [49]. Right-hand side shows the monthly and daily average temperature extremes.[50]

Table 3: Selected representative extreme weather years

Location	W1	W2	W3	S1	S2	S3
Vantaa (Area I)	2010	2020	2016	2017	2018	2010
Sodankylä (Area IV)	2010	2020	2003	2008	2018	2018

The HDD and CDD results from Figure 3 show the annual variation between the heating and cooling demands, as well as the differences between the selected locations. For instance, annual HDD values are 27-39 % lower in Vantaa than Sodankylä, while CDD values are low in both places. Sodankylä also has faced a lot lower daily average temperature (-37°C) than Vantaa (-25°C), requiring different sizing of heating devices. On an annual level, the HDD values in Vantaa can vary by 43 % while Sodankylä has faced a lower annual variation of 21 %.

3.3. Climate change

Future weather data according to RCP2.6, RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios in near-, medium- and long-term were based on future TRY datasets [48], and Coupled Model Intercomparison Project 5 (CMIP5) results for Finland described in [46]. The results for monthly mean temperature changes by these scenarios for Vantaa and Sodankylä are presented in Figure 4, showing larger changes in the long-term with RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios, and during colder months. By 2030, the temperature increases by the RCP scenarios will not differ much, Vantaa changes are from 0.78°C to 1.65°C and Sodankyla from 0.82°C to 2.07°C compared to the baseline. After that, the differences between RCP scenarios start to show and, by 2080, the monthly average temperatures differ by $2.5\text{-}4.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $2.8\text{-}5.1^{\circ}\text{C}$

between RCP2.6 and RCP8.5 in Vantaa and Sodankylä, respectively. This results in an overall increase in monthly temperature by 1.2-5.7 °C in Vantaa by 2080, and 1.2-7.3 °C in Sodankylä by 2080 from baseline. Additionally, during the colder winter months, the increases are 0.0-3.3 °C higher than in warmer summer months. Based on this, it can be assumed that the impact on heating demand would be higher than on the cooling demand. As the change in mean monthly temperature is 0.0-1.6 °C higher in Sodankylä than Vantaa, it can also be assumed that Sodankylä will face larger changes in thermal energy demand.

Figure 4: Changes in mean monthly temperatures in Vantaa and Sodankylä by RCP scenario in short-, medium- and long-term [46, 48].

4. Results

This section presents the results of climate change’s impact on energy demand of detached houses of various energy efficiency in Finland. Results are presented as the average values between different building sizes, unless stated otherwise.

4.1. Existing weather data simulations

The thermal energy demands from existing weather data simulations are presented in Table 4 with comparison to reference values from literature [13, 51, 47]. The reference results from [13] are simulated with the IDA-ICE program for a detached house in Vantaa having different energy efficiency levels, whereas the results from [51] are based on assumptions of thermal energy consumption for a “typical” building from the decade. Both of them include energy demand for domestic hot water, so 35 kWh/m², an estimation from Decree 1010/2017, is subtracted from them to cover this demand, along with appliance consumption from [13] value as they have defined. The estimation for the energy demand of a passive building type is of 25 kWh/m² in South Finland without domestic hot water heating as a boundary level, based on a definition from [47].

Comparing the reference values to a 2018 building in Vantaa shows a resembling performance. For the passive building type, the TRY2020 results are a bit higher than what the reference value suggests, but the difference can be explained by building design options – the case-study building is not designed to meet passive house requirements nor does it include local energy generation. The 1985 building type results are above the reference values in Vantaa, but values from [13] are simulated with slightly higher energy efficiency levels and results from [51] refer to a “typical” building from the era under the current environment, hence, it can be assumed that they are well-renovated or designed to higher energy efficiency. Therefore, all Vantaa simulation results can be deemed acceptable compared to reference values. Comparison to Sodankylä cannot be done directly due to the differences in climate and weather conditions. Therefore, the comparison is conducted according to normalization factors by Finnish Meteorological Institute between different locations in Finland [49] according to their annual HDD values. This gives an estimation

Table 4: Average thermal energy demand by different building types and weather scenarios under current climate conditions in Vantaa and Sodankylä. Reference results are from [13, 51] and from [47] for passive building under Vantaa weather conditions, assuming a constant 35 kWh/m² (assumption from Decree 1010/2017) as hot water consumption from original results, unless otherwise stated. Values are averages over three building sizes, and diff-% describes the difference between max and min results between the buildings.

Building Type	Ref	Vantaa					Sodankyla				
		TRY2020	W1	W2	S1	S2	TRY2020	W1	W2	S1	S2
1985 Avg. [kWh/m ²]	155-121	175	210	163	172	171	241	265	217	235	261
1985 Diff [%]	-	8	7	10	9	9	4	4	5	4	6
1985 Heat Demand [kWh/m ²]	-	174	207	163	172	167	241	265	217	235	260
1985 Cooling Demand [kWh/m ²]	-	1	3	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	2
2018 Avg. [kWh/m ²]	81-50	63	83	55	60	68	94	108	84	88	102
2018 Diff [%]	-	16	12	26	18	12	11	10	11	12	11
2018 Heat Demand [kWh/m ²]	-	59	75	55	57	58	93	107	82	88	98
2018 Cooling Demand [kWh/m ²]	-	4	7	0	3	10	1	1	3	1	4
Passive Avg. [kWh/m ²]	25	31	47	19	27	38	54	66	47	48	58
Passive Diff [%]	-	14	9	50	18	14	11	8	12	14	10
Passive Heat Demand [kWh/m ²]	-	25	39	19	22	27	52	64	43	47	53
Passive Cooling Demand [kWh/m ²]	-	6	9	1	5	11	2	2	4	1	5

that the energy demand of a similar building in Sodankylä in the current climate is 1.55 times higher than in Vantaa. With this estimation, results from Sodankylä are generally within that range and can thus be used.

The results show that the total thermal demand between maximum and minimum weather files in Vantaa vary 23-59% with lower variation for the 1985 building, and higher for the Passive building. In Sodankylä, the annual variations are smaller, between 18 and 29%. Dividing the annual thermal energy demand to heating and cooling, the dominance of heating demand is evident, varying from 100-70% share of the total thermal energy demand, higher for 1985 buildings than the 2018 or passive buildings. The 1985 building type has higher heating demand, whereas 2018 and passive buildings have higher cooling demands. This results in overall high (W1) and low (W2) demands. For cooling, the high cooling (S2) weather resulted in the highest cooling demands, but this was not the case for low cooling (S1) weather, as for Vantaa W2 resulted in lower cooling demand. This indicates that to assess cooling demand, the temperature, and CDD cannot be the only used parameters.

The monthly energy demands for the selected weather files are presented in Figure 5 separately for each building type for both locations, presenting the year-long trend of thermal energy demands; heating in winter and, in some years, cooling in summer, especially July. The results show that the heating period is longer than the cooling period and that there is more variation in winter than in summer months. The monthly demand is flatter for more energy-efficient building types (2018 and Passive), which suggests more stable year-long demand.

The peak demand results from existing weather file simulations are presented in Table 5. These results show the difficulty in defining a suitable weather file for assessing peak demands, as the lowest heating results come from W2, but the peak heating is with W1 or W3 depending on building type and location. For cooling, the lowest values are achieved with W2 or W3 in Vantaa, and with W1 in Sodankylä, even though S1 was expected to provide those results.

Figure 5: Monthly Energy Demands by 1985, 2018, and Passive building types in Vantaa and Sodankylä for every weather scenarios.

The peak cooling demand was observed with S2 in Vantaa and Sodankylä. S3 is the same as S2 in Sodankylä, which would indicate that peak cooling demand can be estimated with a year of the highest CDD instead of the highest average daily temperature. These results show that to estimate peak demand, daily weather values are not enough, and different building types require varying weather data for the same assessment. This may impact future energy system evaluation, as peak demands are not reached with similar weather conditions.

Table 5: The Heating and Cooling Peaks with different building types and weather scenarios.

Building Type	Vantaa						Sodankylä					
	TRY2020	W1/S3	W2	W3	S1	S2	TRY2020	W1	W2	W3	S1	S2/S3
1985 Heat Peak [W/m ²]	79	92	55	78	81	72	95	91	86	98	79	95
1985 Cooling Peak [W/m ²]	13	21	3	2	10	28	7	2	6	15	3	21
2018 Heat Peak [W/m ²]	32	39	21	39	35	31	49	47	44	52	39	45
2018 Cooling Peak [W/m ²]	19	22	9	11	25	27	18	11	18	20	19	22
Passive Heat Peak [W/m ²]	22	25	12	27	23	20	35	34	32	37	28	32
Passive Cooling Peak [W/m ²]	19	21	11	14	24	25	19	14	17	20	19	21

Comparing peak demands, the difference between minimum and maximum in Vantaa was 40-56 % for heating and 56-90 % for cooling. For Sodankylä the differences were 12-14 % and 32-92 % for heating and cooling peak demands,

respectively. The passive building had a relatively larger difference between the heating peaks than the 2018 and 1985 building types. Conversely, the 1985 building type had a larger difference for the cooling peaks than the 2018 and passive buildings. The results indicate that all the building types need the same-sized cooling systems, but they are more oversized for the 1985 building types for cooler years than its energy-efficient counterparts.

4.2. Changes in thermal energy demand in near-, medium, and long-term

4.2.1. Annual thermal energy demand

The results for thermal energy demand changes according to climate change are divided into different categories looking into the impact of various climate change and weather scenarios. Firstly, the results from different climate change scenarios with TRY are presented in Figure 6. These results show that, in every climate change scenario, the thermal energy demand is expected to decrease with each building type under typical-weather years in near-, medium, and long-term time horizons (on average over the three building types, all RCP scenarios and both locations 2.2-22.9 kWh/m², 3.1-43.2 kWh/m², and 3.2-74.6 kWh/m², respectively). Therefore, under these conditions, heating demand of the building decreases more than what is the increase in cooling (5.0-75.7 kWh/m² decrease in heating by 2080 compared to 0.1-6.8 kWh/m² increase in cooling demand averaged over all buildings, all RCP scenarios and both locations). We can see a similar trend with the results from [19] regarding their direct electric heated building and the 2018 building type. As Jylhä et al. [19] used Special Report on Emissions Scenarios (SRES) climate scenarios, 2100 as the end year, different simulation variables, and different energy efficiency levels for buildings, a direct comparison is difficult, but their smaller changes (-8%, -13% and -16% for 2030, 2050, and interpolated 2080, respectively) follow quite closely to the changes received here with RCP4.5 (-8%, -12% and -17% for 2030, 2050, and interpolated 2080) and their larger changes (-10%, -15% and -27% for 2030, 2050 and interpolated 2080) follow RCP8.5 results here with 2018 building type (-9%, -16% and -25%) in Vantaa. This validates the results obtained here with ISO 52016-1 based model under future climatic conditions.

Figure 6: The development of total thermal energy demand under the RCP climate change scenarios with TRY weather data. Ref. values are interpolated for 2080.

The difference between RCP2.6 and RCP8.5 results in 2080 is 34-49 kWh/m² (28 – 29%) for the 1985 building type while for the passive building type the same difference is 4-11 kWh/m² (15 – 32%). The decrease in average absolute thermal energy over all building types by 2080 is smaller in Vantaa (3.2-54.0 kWh/m²) than in Sodankylä (6.7-74.6 kWh/m²). These are caused by the smaller energy demand under the existing weather conditions and the higher increase in cooling demand in Vantaa (0.7-6.8 kWh/m²) than in Sodankylä (0.1-3.9 kWh/m²). This corresponds with the findings from subsection 3.3 where Sodankylä was found to have a higher temperature rise than Vantaa, and the temperature increase was more profound during winter than summer periods, leading to an overall decrease in thermal energy demand.

In Figure 7 the inspection of the results is expanded to various weather scenarios, presented by the changes in total thermal, heating, and cooling energy demands. As discussed earlier, the original weather files may not always produce extreme results, hence the results here are based on average minimum and maximum values of the building types among the climate change scenario and year. The results in Figure 7 confirm the trend from the TRY results by showing reductions in total thermal and heating energy demands, and an increase in cooling energy demand. The results indicate the magnitude of change for each RCP scenario and period, and how the changes in energy demands for the extreme results compare to TRY or medium results. The results for total thermal energy demand and its change from today's climate are presented in Table 6.

Figure 7: The comparison of total, heating and cooling energy demands between TRY and extreme weather files in Vantaa and Sodankylä for 1985, 2018 and passive building types. Comparisons are done according to building types, climate change scenarios, and years.

Figure 7 and Table 6 show the continuous decrease in total thermal energy demand under all the extreme and TRY weather scenarios from the current climate. Hence, total thermal energy can be assumed to decrease at least until 2080, notwithstanding the RCP scenario. Considering the differences between the extreme results separately, thermal energy demand decreases more during minimum demand than TRY or maximum demand year with 1985 and 2018 building types in Vantaa, while the opposite happens for all the other scenarios. This is likely caused by the “special” minimum demand year in Vantaa having both the lowest heating and cooling demands in today's climate, which carries over to future results with the mentioned year having a lower increase in cooling demand than others, while having a similar reduction in heating demand. This results in an operational range increasing for 1985 and 2018 building types in Vantaa in the future whereas in Sodankylä, they face decreasing or constant (less than 0.1 kWh/m²) change after each time period. For the passive building type, the range increases in Vantaa for RCP2.6 and RCP4.5 scenarios and decreases with RCP8.5, as well as in all Sodankylä scenarios. The passive and 2018 building types start to have overlapping demand ranges by 2080 with RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios when passive buildings in a high thermal energy demand year can have higher demand than 2018 under a low thermal energy demand year. With similar weather conditions, the passive building still has the lowest thermal energy demand in all the scenarios. The 1985 building type also has the highest heating demands of all, in contrast to the passive building having the highest cooling demands. Heating demand also stays dominant in all cases except for passive buildings under RCP8.5 and S2 scenario in 2080, when cooling can take 60% of the total thermal energy demand.

The extreme results for heating and cooling show the absolute changes in the high energy demand categories. The maximum heating demand in Vantaa can decrease 20-58 kWh/m², 9-24 kWh/m² and 5-15 kWh/m² for 1985, 2018, and passive building types, respectively, by 2080. This results in a 10-39% decrease of maximum annual heat demand with the relative change higher for the building of originally lower heating demand. For Sodankylä, the decrease in maximum heating demand is bigger, 25-75 kWh/m² for 1985 building type, 12-34 kWh/m² for the 2018 building type,

Table 6: The annual thermal energy demands of building types under RCP climate scenarios in 2030, 2050, and 2080 in kWh/m² (change of the extreme results from today's climate in kWh/m²).

	Vantaa			Sodankylä		
	1985	2018	PE	1985	2018	PE
2030						
RCP2.6	148-198 (-12-15)	50-79 (-4-5)	17-45 (-2-3)	200-247 (-17-18)	78-101 (-6-7)	43-61 (-4-5)
RCP4.5	145-196 (-15-18)	49-78 (-5-6)	16-45 (-2-3)	198-244 (-19-20)	77-99 (-7-9)	42-61 (-5)
RCP8.5	144-195 (-16-19)	48-77 (-5-7)	16-44 (-3)	195-242 (-22-23)	76-98 (-8-10)	41-60 (-6)
2050						
RCP2.6	143-193 (-17-20)	48-77 (-6-7)	16-44 (-3-4)	194-240 (-23-25)	76-98 (-9-10)	41-60 (-6)
RCP4.5	135-187 (-23-28)	45-75 (-8-10)	15-43 (-4)	186-232 (-31-33)	73-94 (-12-14)	39-57 (-8-9)
RCP8.5	127-180 (-30-36)	42-73 (-10-13)	14-42 (-5)	177-222 (-41-43)	69-90 (-15-18)	36-55 (-11)
2080						
RCP2.6	141-192 (-18-22)	47-77 (-6-8)	16-44 (-3-4)	193-239 (-24-25)	75-97 (-9-11)	41-59 (-6-7)
RCP4.5	124-178 (-33-39)	41-72 (-11-14)	14-42 (-5-6)	173-195 (-44-46)	68-89 (-16-19)	35-54 (-12)
RCP8.5	102-160 (-50-61)	34-67 (-16-21)	13-39 (-7-8)	148-191 (-69-74)	59-78 (-25-30)	29-48 (-17-18)

and 8-22 kWh/m² for passive building type by 2080. In relative terms, these changes are lower than in Vantaa, being -10-35 %, due to higher original heating demand. The impact of the RCP scenario to maximum heating demand is significant by 2080, e.g., in Vantaa RCP4.5 results in 9-12 % lower maximum annual heating demand than RCP2.6, while RCP8.5 results in 20-30 % and 12-20 % lower maximum heating demands than RCP2.6 and RCP4.5 scenarios, respectively. The RCP scenario impact is similar in Sodankylä, where RCP4.5 has 9-11 % lower maximum heating demand than RCP2.6 and RCP8.5 has 21-26 % and 13-17 % lower heating demands than RCP2.6 and RCP4.5.

As seen before, the increase in maximum cooling demand is smaller than the decrease in heating demand. By 2080, the maximum annual cooling demand increase is between 2-10 kWh/m² in all building types in Vantaa and 1-5 kWh/m² in Sodankylä. Comparing the RCP scenarios, their differences become equally evident in heating demand changes. RCP4.5 has 14-34 % and 19-36 % higher maximum cooling demand than RCP2.6 in Vantaa and Sodankylä, respectively. RCP8.5 then results in 41-115 % and 23-61 % increase in maximum annual cooling demand to RCP2.6 and RCP4.5 in Vantaa, along with 59-123 % and 34-64 % increases to RCP2.6 and RCP4.5 in Sodankylä.

4.2.2. Average change in a year

As the long-term change in climate is not linear, neither can the change in the thermal demand in buildings be. The changes in annual thermal energy averages by time period, location, and building type are presented in Figure 8, giving us an indication of the level of change between the time periods. All the demand types seem to follow a similar structure, which is mainly impacted by the RCP scenario. With RCP2.6 and RCP4.5 the largest change in annual average values is by 2030, after which the medium- and long-term changes are less evident. With RCP2.6 scenario, the annual average change practically stagnates by 2080, whereas with RCP4.5 scenario the changes in 2050-2080 time period are 55-44 % smaller than from the current to 2030 climate. The average annual changes under RCP8.5 scenario are more stable, having less than 0.13 kWh/m² changes between the time periods. These changes between the RCP scenarios follow the overall trend of the average temperature rise in these scenarios in Finland,

Figure 8: The average annual changes between time periods in all locations, according to their climate change scenario and averaged over all the weather scenarios for 1985, 2018 and passive building types.

which can be seen in [46]. The impact of constantly increasing temperature is the most visible with expected cooling energy demand change, as with every time period, the cooling demand is growing more than within the previous time period. The largest change per average year occurs with 1985 building type in Sodankylä between 2050 and 2080 time periods and RCP8.5 scenario, where heating energy demand can decrease on average 1.1 kWh/m² per year and total thermal energy demand 1.0 kWh/m². The 2018 building type can face reductions in total thermal energy demand of 0.4 kWh/m² per year and passive building up to 0.3 kWh/m² per year. In absolute terms, these values are not large compared to the annual average thermal demands of mentioned buildings, but as this change occurs every year, over decades it will accumulate to more perceptible outcomes. Additionally, depending on the RCP path, detached houses can either already be facing their largest changes per year, or will continue to face similar annual changes in the long-term. This impacts the design of buildings, as due to their long-age nature, the possible largely varying, and uncertain future conditions need to be taken into account during their design and renovation phases.

4.2.3. Monthly energy demand change

The changes on the total thermal energy demand on a monthly-basis are presented in Figure 9 by the time periods and RCP scenarios as averaged and max-min values. These results show that the energy demand is expected to decrease in January-March and October-December in all cases. The biggest decrease in the energy demand occurs in January with the average change varying between -0.32-3.05 kWh/m² by 2030, -0.43-6.05 kWh/m² by 2050, and -0.43-10.59 kWh/m² by 2080. In contrast, the energy demand increases most in July (up to 0.77 kWh/m² by 2030, 1.39 kWh/m² by 2050 and 2.86 kWh/m² by 2080) with overall increases June-August in Vantaa, but not in Sodankylä. Location-wise, Vantaa faces the smallest decreases and biggest increases in energy demand in absolute terms. Looking more specifically into the different building types; on average, passive buildings have an increase in

Figure 9: The changes on monthly energy demand by 2030, 2050 and 2080 by RCP scenarios on Vantaa and Sodankyla

their thermal energy demand from May to September in Vantaa, and from May to August in Sodankylä already by 2030. On the other end, for the 1985 building type, thermal energy demand increases only during July (and August with RCP8.5 in 2080) in Vantaa, while in Sodankylä it does not increase at all except for July in RCP8.5 scenario in 2080. Hence, the directions of the changes are already visible by 2030, and only their magnitudes change. Yearly variation exists, e.g. passive buildings can have an increase in thermal energy demand already in April, which could indicate an early start of the cooling season.

Figure 10: The peak power demand in the future in Vantaa and Sodankyla by the year, climate change scenario and building type, compared between minimum, TRY (or median) and maximum power results. The heating is in blue, and the cooling in yellow/orange.

4.2.4. Peak energy demands

The changes in the peak power demand are presented in Figure 10 showing the variation of heating and cooling peak power demands between the extreme weather years, and their relation to the “average” weather year. As was discovered in subsection 4.1, the extreme results are not obtained with the same weather files, so results in Figure 10 are based on extreme peaks from all scenarios, and on TRY or median results. The changes of only the maximum peaks are presented in Table 7.

The impact of the age of the building is visible in Figure 10 – the 1985 building type generally has the largest

Table 7: The change of maximum heating/cooling peaks on average by building type, climate change scenario, and year compared to the current climate [W/m²]

	Vantaa			Sodankylä		
	1985	2018	PE	1985	2018	PE
2030						
RCP2.6	-5.0/+2.3	-2.6/+1.4	-2.0/+1.2	-5.6/+2.8	-3.2/+2.4	-2.3/+2.2
RCP4.5	-5.6/+2.6	-2.8/+1.6	-2.0/+1.3	-6.4/+2.8	-3.6/+2.3	-2.5/+2.0
RCP8.5	-5.7/+3.2	-3.0/+1.8	-2.2/+1.4	-6.7/+3.6	-3.8/+2.6	-2.7/+2.2
2050						
RCP2.6	-8.0/+3.0	-3.8/+1.9	-2.7/+1.5	-8.1/+3.4	-4.6/+2.6	-3.2/+2.3
RCP4.5	-8.9/+4.1	-4.4/+2.6	-3.2/+1.9	-9.5/+4.7	-5.4/+3.1	-3.8/+2.6
RCP8.5	-12.4/+5.6	-6.1/+3.5	-4.6/+2.5	-13.2/+6.0	-7.5/+3.7	-5.3/+3.0
2080						
RCP2.6	-8.3/+2.9	-3.9/+2.0	-3.0/+1.4	-7.9/+3.2	-4.5/+2.5	-3.2/+2.2
RCP4.5	-13.5/+5.1	-6.4/+3.4	-4.7/+2.5	-13.8/+5.8	-7.8/+3.6	-5.5/+3.0
RCP8.5	-20.8/+10.1	-10.1/+6.9	-8.0/+5.1	-23.2/+11.0	-13.3/+5.8	-9.4/+4.6

heating and cooling peaks, with the heating peaks being the most dominant of all the building types in both locations. In Vantaa, both 2018 and passive building types have overlapping peak demands, with maximum cooling demand overtaking maximum heating demand in all RCP scenarios with passive building and, by 2080, in 2018 building with RCP8.5 scenario. This would mean that with passive building in Vantaa, the cooling device would need to be sized larger than the heating device. In Sodankylä, peak heating demand stays dominant with all building types, and overlapping of cooling and heating peaks happens only in longer-term horizons, with higher temperature rise scenarios, and with 2018 and passive building types. Overall, the overlapping of heating and cooling peaks would mean that the annual peak thermal energy demand would not have a fixed season with these building types. The maximum thermal energy peak would also decrease along with the decrease of the maximum heating peak, except for the passive building type in Vantaa with RCP8.5 scenario by 2080, where the increasing cooling peak would end up increasing the annual thermal energy peak from the current climate as well.

Looking only into the maximum peaks in Table 7, the decrease in maximum heating peak is larger than the increase in cooling peak in all scenarios. By building types, a 1985 building type would face the largest decrease in heating peak while also having the highest increase in cooling peak. Similarly, the highest changes occur with RCP8.5 scenario by 2080 with all building types. The changes between the RCP scenarios by 2030 are less than 1.1 W/m² after which they start to separate with increasing intensity. Hence, the RCP scenario starts to properly impact the sizing of heating and cooling devices only after 2030. As the heating peak is expected to decrease, sizing it with the current climate will make it “oversized” with time, while with cooling, the increase in its peak will mean that the cooling device will be “undersized” with time, unless the expected increase of future cooling peak is acknowledged during the design phase.

4.3. Impact of the thermal performance level of the buildings

The energy efficiency of a building depends on both the climate and thermal properties of a building. If thermal properties remain the same, then climate change’s impact increases the benefits of energy efficiency. The impact of energy efficiency improvements to thermal energy demand with TRY scenario to peak heating and cooling demands are presented in Figure 11 for Vantaa and Sodankylä, for all building types (1985 to passive buildings). These results support other findings that buildings in Vantaa have lower achievable thermal energy reduction potential from renovation (−144-97 kWh/m²) than similar ones in Sodankylä (−187-131 kWh/m²). The beneficial impact of energy efficiency improvement reduces with time in all climate change scenarios, indicating that the sooner the building is renovated, the higher the cumulative benefit of improvements in terms of reduced energy demand. Generally, the reductions in energy demands are 12-14 kWh/m², 15-27 kWh/m² and 16-47 kWh/m² lower in 2030, 2050, and 2080, respectively from the 2005 value in Vantaa. For Sodankylä, the trend is similar with the energy demand reductions

being 13-17 kWh/m², 18-32 kWh/m² and 19-56 kWh/m² lower in 2030, 2050, and 2080 respectively compared to the same action with 2005 values. Additionally, the climate change scenario impacts on how the renovation would improve the energy efficiency of the building. Scenarios with higher temperature rise have a lower potential of reducing the thermal energy demand of buildings with the difference becoming more pronounced with time. In Vantaa, RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios reduce the energy demand by 2-3 kWh/m² less by 2030 compared to RCP2.6 scenario. By 2050, RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios have 6 kWh/m² and 12 kWh/m² lower thermal energy reduction potential compared to RCP2.6, which responds to 13 kWh/m² and 31 kWh/m² in 2080, respectively. In Sodankylä the differences between the scenarios are higher, with RCP4.5 having 15 kWh/m² and RCP8.5 37 kWh/m² lower improvements from energy efficiency renovations by 2080.

Figure 11: Comparison of the changes in energy efficiency improvement, and peak heating and cooling values in Vantaa and Sodankylä between 1985, 2018 and passive building types.

Apart from thermal energy demand reductions, renovations impact the sizing of heating and cooling devices. Figure 11 shows the changes in the peak heating and cooling power values for renovating 1985 type to 2018 and passive buildings. These values can be used as a representative to show the development of sizing the heating and cooling devices of a building with time. For the peak heat power demand, the reduction due to renovation is 52-65 W/m² in Vantaa and 47-61 W/m² in Sodankylä. Similar to thermal energy demand, the differences between the peak heating power demands of the building types decrease with time. By 2030, the peak heating demand reduction due to energy efficiency renovation is 3-4 W/m² lower than in 2005 in Vantaa. By 2050 it is 5-8 W/m² and by 2080 5-13 W/m² lower than in 2005. In Sodankylä the same renovation results 3-4 W/m², 5-8 W/m², and 5-14 W/m² lower reductions in peak heating demand by 2030, 2050, and 2080, respectively, compared to 2005. This is a smaller change than the reduction in thermal energy demand, except in the RCP8.5 scenario in 2080, in which the relative changes are approximately equal.

The impact of building renovation on the peak cooling demand shows opposite results to peak heating and thermal energy demands, as improving the energy efficiency level of the building will increase the differences between the peak cooling demands of building types with time. Building renovation will decrease peak cooling demand 0-8 W/m² in both Vantaa and Sodankylä, showing little difference in results. Timewise, the reductions from building renovation from 1985 to passive building are 1 W/m², 1-3 W/m² and 1-6 W/m² higher by 2030, 2050, and 2080, respectively, compared to 2005 results. This would suggest that cooling devices' power need reduces due to energy efficiency

renovation, but the buildings benefit more from the renovation with time and the higher the temperature rise in Finland. Nonetheless, compared to the reductions in peak heating power need, cooling power demand has much less impact in absolute terms.

5. Discussion

The results of this study show that, due to climate change, buildings will consume less thermal energy in the future as the decrease in heating demand is expected to be higher than the increase in cooling demand. While in almost every scenario, heating will remain the dominant thermal energy demand source, future buildings seem to become more diverse with their thermal energy, not only with annual demand, but with peak demand as well. Especially as cooling needs will increase in Finland in the future, and the increase in its peak demand is universal for all building types. Annual cooling demand values are still relatively low for 1985 building types, questioning the need for cooling devices, especially if they are used only during peak demand times. This will require weighting between potential discomfort and the economic viability of cooling device installation.

The reduction of thermal energy demands in the future is also paradoxical as all buildings seem to reduce their energy demands without taking any action. In contrast, a larger temperature rises will require more adaptation measures to tackle increasing cooling demands. Overall, the results suggest that renovating buildings will always be more impactful than temperature rise. This is in line with the findings of [52]. Therefore, even though climate change requires adaptation measures for buildings, improving energy efficiency will always be more beneficial than relying on reduced thermal energy demand due to climate change. The adaptation requirements were visible also in the monthly thermal energy demand – buildings had lower thermal energy demands during winter months and, on average, demand increased in the summer, especially in July, due to cooling. Not only does this indicate the increase of cooling periods, but also their growth in length. Yet, these results are based on morphed future weather files, assuming that weather profiles would be similar in the future, which may not be the case. The future climate could produce, for instance, longer heat wave periods than today, which would demand more adaptation measures.

Results of this study also indicate that for RCP2.6 and RCP4.5 scenarios, the largest decreases in building thermal energy demands are already happening, and the impacts will balance out, whereas for RCP8.5 the changes will continue all the way until 2080. Considering potential renovation benefits, the study found that thermal energy demand reductions are higher the earlier the renovation is made. These results suggest that earlier mitigation actions are more beneficial, and they help also lowering later mitigation and adaptation requirements. This translates to lower-sized cooling devices later on.

The impact of location was another important factor in this study. The results indicated a larger thermal energy demand decrease in the colder Sodankylä area. This finding is in line with one from Berardi and Jafarpur [53], who discovered that buildings with higher heating demands in cold climates have the highest potential in improving their energy use intensity in the future. Berardi and Jafarpur [53] also concluded that buildings with better thermal insulation are less affected by climate change. This is supported by the results achieved here, as passive buildings were found to have the least changes to their current thermal energy demand overall. Therefore, it would seem that the trend and results discovered here would be applicable to other cold and heating-dominated countries, expanding the relevance of results.

The results are not without some limitations. Uncertainty arises from the used weather and climate scenarios, as the results from the original extreme weather files in the study did not always result in maximum and minimum total and peak thermal energy demands, highlighting the difficulty of defining them. Especially with minimum total cooling demand, and peak demands, additional variables to temperature may be needed to determine the suitable weather files. In this study, it led to assessing the operational range through all selected scenarios, even if they were not originally selected to be used in heating, cooling, or peak demand assessments. Since the same weather file may not produce the same end results, it highlights the difficulty of selecting suitable weather files. This may indicate that extreme weather file selection may have to be building-type-specific. Appending the simulations with other weather file types, like e.g., Design Summer Year (DSY) [54] could help in providing more comprehensible results. Similarly, RCP climate change scenarios and simulation results from GCMs contain their own, embedded, uncertainties. Other limitations can be traced to the used thermal behavior model and the lack of dynamic parts, requiring add-ons to the models. As the model was designed to operate without accurate information about the building outside of “general” regulative values, some assumptions, and simplifications needed to be made, all of which may have impacted the accuracy of

the results. The simulations were selected to exclude passive, preventative, and behavioral actions or measures. This is definitely a limitation in broader use of the results, as all mentioned factors can be utilized in both mitigation and adaptation measures in buildings. For instance, external shading devices can be used to reduce solar irradiance and cooling demand. Or users in the future could have different temperature set-points, either lower or higher than in this study. These, together with other system specifics, affect thermal energy needs.

Overall, the study demonstrates that, when designing buildings with the intent of reducing energy demand and GHG emissions, future climate projections will need to be included in the assessment. One good example of this is a potential future zero energy building; without considering the future climate, it is possible that the building misses the zero energy goal in its future operations [55]. Even though zero-energy buildings and their operation and design go beyond the topic of this study, it can still be mentioned that, without considering thermal energy needs in the future, the net zero requirements may be difficult to achieve. At the same time, adaptive measures needed in the future should be included in buildings already now, reducing the need for additional renovations, whilst ensuring inhabitant comfort levels from the beginning.

6. Conclusion

This study investigated the development of the future thermal energy demand in buildings under cold, Nordic settings. The novelty of the work related to considering the thermal energy demand development in detached houses for both northern and southern parts of Finland under Representative Concentration Pathways on near-, medium- and long-term horizons (2030, 2050, 2080, respectively). The work was conducted by creating a thermal building model based on standards and local building regulation and simulating it with suitable current and future weather data, of which future extreme conditions were created during the study through statistical down-scaling method called morphing.

The thermal energy demand of detached houses in Finland is expected to decrease due to climate change in the near-, medium- and long-term time horizon. By 2080, the expected decrease is 3-75 kWh/m² on average under TRY weather scenario, with heating demand decreasing by 5-76 kWh/m² and cooling demand increasing by 0.1-7 kWh/m². The differences between the RCP2.6 and RCP8.5 scenarios are 34-49 kWh/m² and 4-11 kWh/m² for 1985 and passive building types, respectively, by 2080. Location-wise the decrease in total thermal demand under TRY weather scenario is 3.5-20.6 kWh/m² lower in Vantaa than in Sodankylä. Considering annual change between time periods, the highest changes are occurring between the current and 2030 climate for RCP2.6 and RCP4.5 scenarios, after which they start to balance off. For RCP8.5 scenario, the change is steadier and continues all the way to 2080. For heating and cooling peak demands, the maximum heating peak is expected to decrease by 3-23 W/m² which is more than what the cooling peak increases (1-10 W/m²) by 2080. Yet in the long-term, especially with passive buildings in Vantaa, cooling peaks can become the dominant thermal energy demand peak.

Improving the energy efficiency of buildings will always lead to lower energy demand, in terms of both total and peak demands. By 2080, the change from the 1985 building type to the passive building level is resulting in a 16-56 kWh/m² lower energy intensity than today, indicating that, with time, renovation becomes less financially feasible than in today's climate. For peak demands, changes to passive building levels result in a 47-65 W/m² lower heating and a 0-8 W/m² lower cooling peak demands. Changes in heating peak follow the same trend as total thermal energy demand change, the improvement in 2080 results in a 5-14 W/m² lower decrease than today. For cooling peak demand, the opposite is true. In 2080, the change from the 1985 building type to the passive building can decrease the peak cooling demand by 1-6 W/m² more than today. In all cases, the end result shows the benefits of early onset energy efficiency improvement.

These results provide guidelines for assessing the thermal energy demands and design of buildings under future climate, supporting the early improvements to the energy efficiency level of the buildings as a mitigation and adaptation tool. This assessment can be further appended with considerations of different building types and ages, having varying building technical systems, to study how these buildings will operate under future climate conditions. Including possible renovation strategies, a more comprehensive analysis of future energy systems could be conducted. The limitations of this study include using simplified weather scenarios, sometimes resulting in contradicting results, and the lack of passive, preventative, and behavioral measures, which all have their impact on the building's thermal energy needs. Further developing the model to include various heating and cooling systems can also help in future consideration to evaluate and design future energy system requirements.

7. Data availability

Datasets related to this article can be found at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8035365> for created extreme weather data, which was created with a morphing tool found at: <https://github.com/japulk/Weather-Morphing-Tool>. The used building thermal model version is available at: https://github.com/jeanlouisnico/SBuM/tree/CCweather_version.

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9. CRediT authorship contribution statement

Jari Pulkkinen: Conceptualization, Data Curation, Formal Analysis, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Software, Resources, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Jean-Nicolas Louis:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Supervision, Visualization, Writing - Review and editing, Funding acquisition **Vincent Debusschere:** Writing – review and editing, Supervision. **Eva Pongracz:** Writing - Review and editing; Supervision, Funding acquisition

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